

Enhancing Underwater Image Quality through Image Processing

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Abstract— Underwater images find application in various fields, like marine research, inspection of aquatic habitat, underwater surveillance, identification of minerals, and more. Longer wavelengths are absorbed by water at greater depths. Due to the greater wavelength, red is absorbed and the images seem primarily bluish-green. Images suffer greatly as a result of these phenomena, which causes low contrast, color distortion, and poor visibility. Underwater photos must therefore be improved in order to retain the important information they provide and make them suitable for a variety of uses.

The proposed system enhances underwater image quality through image processing techniques. The system includes color correction, image sharpening and image fusion methods and aims to provide more accurate solutions for underwater image enhancement. This system offers real-time adaptability, making it suitable for applications like underwater robotics, live video streaming, and autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs). It has the potential to significantly impact scientific research, exploration, and underwater technology by improving underwater image quality and versatility.

Keywords: Underwater image enhancement, Color Compensation, Color correction, Contrast enhancement, Image Sharpening, Fusion.

I. INTRODUCTION

The objective of this study is to explore the application of image processing in enhancing underwater image quality. Image enhancement is the process of improving the quality of the input image so that it would be easily understood by viewers. Image enhancement modifies the image's visual impression on the viewer while also improving the image's information content. Enhancement of images makes their

features more intense. It draws attention to image elements like contrast and edges to make photo displays more beneficial for research and analysis.

Enhancement increases the active range of the selected visual features, making them easier to identify. The two main issues with underwater photographs are low visibility and poor colour contrast. These issues arose from light dispersion and refraction when light entered a medium that was denser than rarer.

Scattering results in light blurring and a decrease in color contrast. In addition to the natural water, the presence of creatures and other materials in the water also contributes to the impact of water on underwater photos. Researchers have developed a wide range of strategies and tactics to address the issue of improving underwater images.

By making underwater scenes more visually appealing, the technique of increasing underwater image quality seeks to overcome these issues. The final objective is to enhance overall underwater imagery quality, fix colour distortions, and bring out hidden details—all while protecting important data.

The proposed method for improving underwater image quality using image processing offers a thorough and advanced approach to dealing with the particular difficulties in taking detailed and crisp underwater photos. The three key methods included in the system—color correction, image sharpening, and image fusion—all contribute greatly to raising the overall quality of underwater photos.

Image sharpening improves edges and fine details in underwater images damaged by light scattering and waterborne particles, allowing researchers and professionals to conduct in-depth analyses.

Image fusion effectively combines several image sources or views to improve visibility of underwater objects and structures. This comprehensive technique is useful for scientific study, surveillance, mineral identification, and industrial inspections in underwater environments.

The suggested method improves underwater imaging quality by properly restoring colour, enhancing sharpness, and integrating information, enabling better knowledge of underwater ecosystems and facilitating decision-making in a variety of businesses that rely on high-quality underwater photographs.

Red, Green, and Blue (RGB) channels of a picture each correspond to a distinct colour component of the image. To produce desired visual effects, image processing procedures like colour correction require altering the values in these channels. The RGB channels may be individually changed in underwater image enhancement to correct for colour aberrations brought on by the absorption and scattering qualities of water. The overall colour balance and accuracy of the image can be enhanced by adjusting the values in each channel, producing underwater photos that are clearer and more aesthetically pleasing.

Figure 1: Original Image and its histogram

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Regarding enhancing underwater image quality, Chang et al. [1] proposed a mean-variance analysis technique to enhance the contrast of palm bone X-ray radiographs by partitioning grayscale images into four associated images and utilizing quad histogram equalization. Experimental results showed superiority over global histogram equalization (GHE) and brightness-saving bi-histogram equalization (BBHE) techniques. Hitam et al. [2] introduced the mixture Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) color model for enhancing underwater images. Operating on RGB and HSV color models and combining results using Euclidean norm, the method showed less mean square error and higher peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) compared to other methods, facilitating effective coral reef classification. Khan et al. [3] proposed Bi- and Multi-histogram equalization methods for contrast improvement in digital

images, maintaining the natural look while enhancing contrast. Simulation results demonstrated enhanced contrast preservation of brightness and natural appearance in trial images. Talha et al. [4] presented Balanced Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (BCLAHE) for Adaptive Dynamic Range Compression (ADRC) of real-time medical pictures. The method yielded high-quality results with improved local information preservation compared to global histogram equalization. Shelda Mohan and T.R. Mahesh [5] utilized Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) to tune enhancement parameters of Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization, preserving local data and details in mammogram images while providing superior contrast enhancement. Senthilkumaran N and Thimmiraja J [6] compared Global Histogram Equalization (GHE), Local Histogram Equalization (LHE), Brightness Preserving Dynamic Histogram Equalization (BPDHE), and Adaptive Histogram Equalization (AHE) for MRI brain image enhancement using various quality measures, highlighting their diverse performance. Setiawan et al. [7] employed Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) to enhance color retinal images, proposing a method utilizing CLAHE in the G channel for improved image quality, validated through visual observation. Sowmyashree et al. 2014[8] have presented a relative study of the different image enhancement methods used for enhancing images of the bodies under the water. It also describes the various properties of water due to which the underwater images are distorted and degraded. Erturk et al. [9] introduced an algorithm based on Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) to improve underwater image visibility, providing finer results compared to traditional methods by decomposing spectral parts into Intrinsic Mode Functions (IMFs) and combining them for enhanced visual features. Galdran et al. [10] proposed the Red Channel method to recover colors associated with short wavelengths in underwater images, akin to the Dark Channel method for haze-degraded images, resulting in contrast recovery. Experimental results supported the efficacy of the Red Channel method.

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III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed approach is implemented in the following step-by-step process for enhancing underwater image quality:

Figure 2: Flow of proposed system

- A. Data collection: Kaggle dataset was used to collect the data.
- B. Compensation of Red-Blue or Red Channel: adjusting of Red-Blue or Red Channel of the input image.
- C. Color correction: Gray World Algorithm is used to achieve color correction and balance in an image.
- D. Contrast Enhancement: Global Histogram Equalization is used for contrast enhancement of the image.
- E. Image Sharpening: Unsharp mashing is used for Image Sharpening.
- F. Fusion: PCA-Based Fusion and Average Based Fusion are performed.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

Compensation of RB or R channel:

Compensation of the RB or R channel is a colour correction technique for adjusting and balancing the colour channels in an RGB image. In this phase, the input image's Red or Red-Blue (RB) channel must be adjusted. To improve the overall colour representation in the image, compensation may involve correcting colour imbalances or improving colour qualities.

Figure 3: Original and RB Compensated Image

Gray World Algorithm:

The Gray World method is a colour correction technique used in image processing to balance the colours in an image and make it look more natural. An image's colour balancing and colour correction can be accomplished with the Gray World Algorithm. It assumes that the average colour in a well-balanced image is gray and adjusts the colour channels accordingly. The algorithm's goal is to eliminate colour casts while also improving overall colour quality.

Figure 4: Compensated Image and White balanced image

Global Histogram Equalization

Global histogram equalisation is an image processing technique that enhances contrast and improves an image's overall brightness distribution. Global Histogram Equalisation is a technique for enhancing contrast throughout an entire image. It improves contrast and detail visibility by redistributing the image's pixel intensity values to create a more uniform histogram. This step improves the image's overall contrast and luminance.

Figure 5: White Balanced Image and Contrast enhanced Image

Unsharp Masking

Unsharp masking is an image processing technique used to enhance the details and edges in an image by creating a sharpened version of the original. Unsharp masking is a sharpening technique used to enhance edges and fine

details in the image. It involves creating a high-pass filtered version of the image (the "sharp" component) and then combining it with the original image to emphasize edges and details. This step enhances the sharpness and fine details in the image.

Figure 6: Original, White Balanced and Sharpened Image

IMAGE FUSION PCA Based Fusion

Principal Component Analysis (PCA)-based fusion is an image fusion technique that leverages the principles of PCA, a dimensionality reduction method, to combine the strengths of multiple images.

Figure 7: Sharpened, Contrast enhanced and PCA Based fusion Image

Average Based Fusion

Average fusion is a method of combining two or more images by taking the average of corresponding pixel values. This technique is commonly used in image processing and computer vision for blending or fusing images to create a composite image.

Figure 8: Sharpened, Contrast enhanced and Average Based fusion Image

V. RESULTS

Based on the metrics, system's performance may be examined. SSM quantifies the similarity between two images, whereas PSNR assesses how well an image reconstruction compares to the original. These metrics would be computed by contrasting the system's improved underwater photographs with reference photos. The dataset that was used, the quality of the original underwater photos, and the efficiency of the system's picture enhancement methods would all affect the particular outcomes. Better

picture quality and similarity are typically indicated by greater PSNR and SSM values, respectively. Data needed to assess the system's performance in terms of PSNR and SSM metrics might be obtained by running experiments using various underwater photos and enhancement methods.

PSNR (Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio): PSNR is a widely used statistic for assessing image and video quality. By contrasting it with the original, reference image, it assesses the quality of a compressed or reconstructed image. The PSNR, which measures the objective difference between the reconstructed and original images, is represented in decibels (dB). Better quality is indicated by higher PSNR values. To assess the amount of quality lost during compression, utilise PSNR. It aids in the algorithmic optimisation of codec makers.

SSIM (Structural Similarity Index): SSIM is a popular image quality assessment metric that calculates the structural similarity between a reference (original) image and a distorted (reconstructed) image. The apparent structural and brightness changes that people are more sensitive to are taken into consideration by SSIM, as compared to PSNR (Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio), which concentrates on pixel-wise differences. The luminance (brightness), contrast (difference in contrast), and structure (structural similarity) components are used to generate the SSIM measure. A value between -1 and 1 can be used to express it, with 1 denoting full similarity between the reference and distorted images. A decimal number between -1 and 1, representing perfect anti-correlation, 0 denoting no similarity, and 1 representing perfect similarity, is the resulting SSIM index.

Figure 9: Metrics of Original and compensated image

Figure 10: Metrics of Compensated and White balanced image

Figure 11: Metrics of White balanced and sharpened image

Figure 12: Metrics of White balanced and contrast enhanced image

Figure 13: Metrics of sharpened image and PCA based fused image

Figure 14: Metrics of Contrast enhanced and PCA based fused image

Figure 15: Metrics of sharpened image and average fused image

Figure 16: Metrics of Contrast enhanced and average fused image

VI. CONCLUSION

The suggested approach makes use of a number of image processing methods to improve the quality of underwater images in a comprehensive way. By combining techniques like the Gray World Algorithm for colour balance, white balancing, image sharpening, histogram equalisation for contrast improvement, PCA and average based fusion for noise reduction, it solves issues including low contrast, colour distortion, and haze. This technology serves a variety of purposes in autonomous underwater vehicles, surveillance, and marine research. Future developments might include expanding enhancement approaches to additional electromagnetic spectrum regions like infrared and sonar, creating real-time solutions for instantaneous image improvement during missions, and incorporating AI and machine learning for customised upgrades.

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